

STANDARDIZATION OF AYURVEDIC FORMULATION (MARICHYADI VATI) USING HPLC AND HPTLC METHODS

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Abstract : The present investigation was aimed to develop methodology for the standardization of Marichyadi Vati and its raw materials. Standardization was carried using systematic pharmacognostical and physicochemical parameters as per WHO guidelines. The detailed Standardization of Marichyadi Vati, it is concluded that there are no major differences prevailed in the quality of marketed products and laboratory samples of Marichyadi Vati. However, market samples showed slightly better amount of Piperine than the laboratory sample by both methods. This is the first attempt to generate complete set of standards required for the Marichyadi Vati.

Keywords : Marichyadi Vati, Standardization, Piperine

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